

Application of polarography for a simple and rapid screening of chlorophacinone in formulations, cereal grains and cauliflower

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A differential pulse polarographic method for the determination of chlorophacinone at low concentration is developed in agricultural formulations and cereal grains. Well-defined wave/peak is obtained for chlorophacinone in the pH range 2.0–6.0 using universal buffer systems. This is attributed to the facile simultaneous reduction of three carbonyl groups in six-electron reduction process at DME. In addition, dissipation and persistence studies are also made for chlorophacinone on cauliflower.

Chlorophacinone[2-{4-chlorophenyl}phenylacetyl]-1*H*-indene-1,3(2*H*)-dione (1) is widely used as systemic rodenticide¹. Among the analytical techniques reported for the analysis of chlorophacinone, HPLC-DAP method², reversed-phase ion-pair liquid chromatographic method³, HPLC⁴, UV-derivative spectrophotometric methods⁵ are dominant. Besides, coulometric investigations⁶ has also been developed for the quantitative estimation of chlorophacinone.

The reduction mechanism and electrode kinetics of chlorophacinone together with the analysis in formulations and cereal grains is the aim of the present work.

Results and Discussion

Chlorophacinone exhibits only one polarographic wave/peak over the pH range 2.0–6.0 with all the techniques. This wave/peak is attributed to the simultaneous reduction of three carbonyl groups of which two are at positions 1 and 3 of indane ring and the third is of the phenylacetyl ring involving six electrons. No reduction is observed in basic medium ($8 \leq \text{pH} \leq 12$) for carbonyl groups⁷

due to the precipitation of electroactive species. Cyclic voltammetry shows the irreversible nature of the electrode process.

In the present study, controlled potential electrolysis has been carried out with the supporting electrolyte of pH 4.0, because chlorophacinone gives maximum current at this pH and an applied potential is set at -0.22 V. The reduction product formed after controlled potential electrolysis was identified as the corresponding hydroxy derivative by IR spectral studies ($3650\text{--}3250\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The determination of number of electrons (n) involved during the electrode process in chlorophacinone was carried out by millicoulometry at pH 4.0. Accordingly, n is found to be six for three carbonyl groups of chlorophacinone.

Typical kinetic parameters, such as diffusion coefficient and heterogeneous forward rate constant values are calculated⁸ for chlorophacinone with all the techniques. The results are summarized in Table 1. The adsorption-free nature of the electrode process is evidenced from the nearly equal diffusion coefficient values obtained from all the techniques. On the basis of the results as well as on data

Table 1. Typical kinetic data of chlorophacinone

Concn. = 0.5 mM, supporting electrolyte : universal buffer

pH of the supporting electrolyte	DC			CV			DPP		
	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$10^5 D$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$k_{f,h}$ cm s^{-1}	$-E_p$ V	$10^5 D$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$k_{f,h}$ cm s^{-1}	$-E_m$ V	$10^5 D$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$k_{f,h}$ cm s^{-1}
2.0	0.12	2.55	6.91×10^{-4}	0.10	2.51	7.83×10^{-4}	0.11	2.68	7.44×10^{-4}
4.0	0.23	2.32	1.20×10^{-5}	0.22	2.38	7.83×10^{-4}	0.24	2.46	6.98×10^{-5}
6.0	0.28	2.19	4.77×10^{-6}	0.30	2.15	7.83×10^{-4}	0.29	2.27	5.01×10^{-6}

from the literature, the electrode mechanism proposed is presented in Scheme 1.

In acidic medium. ($2.0 < \text{pH} < 6.0$)

Scheme 1

Recovery studies of chlorophacinone : Well-defined and well-resolved peak of chlorophacinone obtained at pH 4.0 is used for the quantitative determination of chlorophacinone in agricultural formulations, cereal grains and cauliflower. Both standard addition and calibration methods were used for the quantitative estimation of chlorophacinone. From the calibration method, the peak height vs concentration plot is found to be linear over the concentration range 1.85×10^{-5} to 3.25×10^{-9} M. The lower detection limit is found to be 1.8×10^{-9} M and is calculated by using the equation, $dl = 3SD/m$. The correlation coefficient (0.967), relative standard deviation (1.86%) and confidence (± 0.0013) show that the precision and accuracy of the method are satisfactory.

The developed procedure was successfully utilized for the determination of chlorophacinone in agricultural formulation, namely, caid, drat and saviac. Assay results for chlorophacinone in agricultural formulations and cereal grains are given in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. No peaks were observed due to blank samples of formulations and cereal grains within the potential studied. Therefore, the proposed dpp method is free from blank samples. The data show that the ingredients present in formulations in addition to chlorophacinone and other constituents present in cereal grains do not interfere in the proposed method.

Table 2. DPP determination of chlorophacinone in agricultural formulations*

Trade name	Labelled amount mg	Amount found mg	Recovery %	Stand dev
Caid	5.0	4.99	99.80	0.013
	10.0	9.87	98.70	0.011
Drat	5.0	4.93	98.60	0.010
	10.0	9.94	99.20	0.015
Saviac	5.0	4.94	98.62	0.017
	10.0	9.91	99.15	0.013

* Averaged results for three determinations

Table 3. Analysis of fortified cereal grains for chlorophacinone by DPP*

Sample	Labelled amount mg	Amount found mg	Recovery %	Stand dev
Maize	5.0	4.98	99.20	0.015
	10.0	9.98	99.60	0.021
	25.0	24.98	98.89	0.022
Barley	5.0	4.98	99.87	0.016
	10.0	9.95	99.50	0.020
	25.0	24.85	98.74	0.025

* Averaged results for three determinations

Investigation was also undertaken to study the persistence of chlorophacinone on cauliflower crop under field conditions. Field experiments were conducted in randomized block design with four replicates at the farm of Agricultural University, Tirupati. After the initiation of curd formation, crop was sprayed with 250 and 500 g. a.i./ha chlorophacinone formulation (caid), and residue analysis was carried out.

The results demonstrate the validity of the polarographic methodology to carry out the determination of this rodenticide at low concentration levels, which may be used in environmental monitoring and food stuff quality control after their suitable extraction into the appropriate organic solvent. The proposed method has major advantages that simplified steps are achieved for the extraction and the solvent consumption is reduced and the analysis time is shortened.

Experimental

Chlorophacinone was obtained from Lipha Laboratories (France). All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Stock solution (1.0×10^{-3} M) was prepared by dissolving the chlorophacinone in dimethylformamide. The desired concentrations of solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solution with the supporting electrolyte. The supporting electrolyte was prepared from 0.05 M citric acid, 0.2 M boric acid and 0.1 M trisodium orthophosphate over the pH range 2.0–12.0. The solution was purged with O_2 -free N_2 gas for 10 min prior to each run. Details of the equipment and experimental procedures are given elsewhere⁹. All measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The dropping mercury electrode used had the following characteristics: area = 0.0223 cm^2 at the drop time 2 s, while the hanging mercury drop electrode [HMDE] had an area of 0.02323 cm^2 . The optimum conditions for the analytical determination at pH 4.0 had a drop time of 2 s, pulse amplitude of 50 mV and an applied potential of -0.23 V .

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